

ACCEPTABILITY OF UPGRADED HOSPITAL INFORMATION SYSTEM (HIS) AMONG NURSES IN A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

Nirmala Kumari¹, & P. K. Suresh Kumar²

1 Research Scholar, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India. E-mail: nirmalak0449@gmail.com, 9964470708

2 Research Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India.

Purpose:

The health industry must embrace information technology to improve treatments. Nurses are the most important users of hospital information systems (HIS) in all healthcare systems, making them the center of care. Therefore, understanding their perspective and how they apply these technologies will help improve hospital information systems.

Design:

Nurses from the wards, intensive care units and emergency departments of a tertiary care teaching hospital participated in a descriptive cross-sectional study. 415 nurses from wards, intensive care units, and emergency departments who met the inclusion or exclusion criteria were surveyed over a two-month period in June and July 2022. Use systematic questionnaires to collect data. Software SPSS version 22 was used for data analysis. Graphs and frequency tables are used to display the results.

Findings:

HIS was deemed to be accurate, user-friendly, and straightforward to employ by the bulk of nurses (61%) who responded to the survey. A little over 42% of nurses report they can't find all the information in their systems, and 35% even say they don't have access to information when they need it. While 16% of nurses claimed that the HIS system's information made their jobs simpler, they also stated that their practice area had duplicate tasks in both the HIS and the records.

Conclusion:

The study concluded that nurses were not finding all the necessary information in the system. Knowledge is not accessible when and where it is needed. However, there is considerable overlap in how nurses use the system to record. To maximize the usability of the system among nurses, the HIS should be regularly reviewed and updated, and information should be communicated to stakeholders in a timely manner.

Key words: Hospital Information System, Nurses, Acceptability, Information Technology

ACCEPTABILITY OF UPGRADED HOSPITAL INFORMATION SYSTEM (HIS) AMONG NURSES IN A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

Nirmala Kumari¹, & P. K. Suresh Kumar²

1 Research Scholar, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University,
Mangalore – 575 001, India. E-mail: nirmalak0449@gmail.com, 9964470708

2 Research Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore –
575 001, India.

Introduction

Hospital information systems (HIS), which are complete, unified, fully certified advanced technologies, are in charge of managing the clinical and administrative parts of hospitals and other healthcare organizations. They are thought to be one of the most crucial elements of health (1). Throughout the 1990s, numerous significant corporate hospitals in India have started utilizing HIS. In fact, every year there are significantly more beds in hospitals and more clinical, administrative, and financial data produced. Despite evidence that HIS can improve individual health and health care provider performance, the result is improved quality, lower cost, acceptance, adoption, and use of HIS by healthcare professionals, leading to increased patient participation in their own healthcare costs. (2) Nursing professionals, who are also patients who either directly or informally benefit from the hospital information system (HIS), make up the bulk of users in every health system. At medical facilities, nurses play a crucial role in providing services. However, nurses need knowledge and skills that are often learned through training in order to use the HIS effectively (3). Thus, it will be advantageous for him to better comprehend their viewpoint and how they employ these technologies. Nurses are free to spend more time caring for patients at the bedside since HIS records take up less time for nurses than paper records. In addition to guaranteeing patient care, the HIS enhances departmental communication and collaboration by making unified data easily accessible.

Statement of the problem

The principle of this study was to determine whether an upgraded hospital information system at a specific tertiary care teaching hospital was acceptable to nurses.

Objective of the study

To study the acceptance of an upgraded Hospital Information System (HIS) among nurses in a selected tertiary care teaching hospital setting.

Scope of the study

The study primarily focuses on the upgraded hospital information system, which will be used and accepted by the nurses from the wards, intensive care units, and emergency department.

Review of Literature

Khalifa M. Alswailem O. (2015) performed a case study on the acceptability and satisfaction of the hospital information system (HIS) in a tertiary care sanitarium. In order to provide information for efficient HIS implementation, the main goal of this study is to look into the factors that might increase or decrease acceptability and pleasure among different healthcare practitioners. Data from different

categories of HIS drug users were immediately gathered using a quantitative collecting technique. There were five sections to the questionnaire. a demographic information portion, a general HIS standing section, a computer availability and vacuity section, and HIS and patient care section, and a fulfillment with HIS section. The findings point to the availability of computers in hospitals as one of the most important factors, allowing medical staff to enter data and retrieve information directly and inconveniently within the healthcare environment. Special emphasis is placed on the accessibility of laptops and computers on buses. Drug dealers asserted that HIS sometimes slowed down the process of providing care and might increase the amount of time patients were kept in the sanitarium. The evaluation concluded with three major areas where he demonstrated potential for improvement. Performance of the system, organizational support, and user comments automated voice recognition reduces workloads and raises the standard of information. In order to provide training and protect time during working hours for drug users to learn and hone their abilities, managerial assistance is essential.

Hsiao J L, Chang H C, Chen RF (2011) conducted the study on Nursing Analysis of Variables Influencing Hospital Information System Relinquishment. The primary purpose of this research is to investigate the critical aspects influencing the acceptability of HIS in Taiwan from a nursing standpoint. Six exogenous variables (system quality, information quality, stoner tone efficacy, comity, elderly operation assistance, and design platoon capability) were employed as hunt factors, based on the technology acceptance paradigm. Nursing personnel from designated case hospitals were included in the study. A total of 545 checks were transferred, with 501 of them being returned. The percentage of correct responses was 91.9. Using several retrogression analyses, the gathered data was anatomized. According to the findings, stoner tone-efficacy, elderly operation support, community, and information quality all had a substantial influence on perceived utility. Moreover, elderly operation support, compliance, and information quality were designed to have a major influence on perceived utility. Furthermore, nurses' perceptions of the HIS's comfort and beneficence were set up to have a considerable influence on system acceptability, accounting for 45.1 of the total explained friction. The study stated that the findings will assist directors in understanding critical factors influencing the creation and usage of SIS and will serve as a benchmark for system development and refinement.

Ismail, A., Jamil, AT, Fareed, A., et al. (2012) performed a qualitative survey on Hospital Information System (HIS) deployment at a Malaysian tertiary hospital. The adoption of hospital information systems in three hospitals was investigated in this study. Serdang Hospital, Selayang Hospital, and Malaysia University Medical Center (UKMMC) In-depth interviews were done with employees representing system providers and end users, and questionnaires were used. The interviewees' ideas are organized into six primary themes and three sub-themes. System development and maintenance, human resources, implementation scope, support systems, usability, and administration were the key difficulties found. The creation and deployment of the hospital information system differ amongst the three institutions. Each system has its own set of benefits and drawbacks. The success of an HIS deployment will be determined by quality human resources, a good support system, user-friendliness, and proper end-user training. According to the report, replacing hardware and software as needed is critical to keeping up with technological breakthroughs and expanding patient numbers. It is envisaged that the SIS will be introduced to all other hospitals through good integration and networking.

R.No.	Research Area	Research focus	References
4	A nurse's viewpoint on the elements influencing hospital information system acceptability	The primary factors influencing nurse perception of HIS acceptability were investigated using a technology acceptance model with six exogenous variables.	Hsiao JL, Chang HC, Chen RF (2011)
5	Adoption and Satisfaction with Hospital Information Systems (HIS): A Tertiary Hospital Case Study	Levels of approval and fulfillment among medical professionals offer strategies for applying HIS effectively.	Khalifa M, Alswailem O (2015)
6	The advantages of health information technology are largely favorable, according to an assessment of current literature.	Aspects of health information technology implementation challenges after reviewing recent health information technology	M. B. Buntin, M. F. Burke, M. C. Hoaglin & D. Blumenthal (2011)
7	Nurses and health Informatics	Experience of nurses in implementing health information technologies over time.	McBride S, Delaney JM, Tietze M (2012)
8	Experience of nurses in implementing health information technologies over time.	Hospital nurses' perceptions on the usefulness of the electronic medical record system	Otieno OG, Toyama H, Asonuma M, Kanai-Pak M, Naitoh K (2007)
9	A Health Manager's Perspective on the Health Management Information System	Health managers' perceptions of health management information systems (HMIS), in light of their organizational environment and the process of decentralization	Qazi MS, Ali M (2009)
10	HMIS use in private sector hospitals among medical staff	Health problems can be reduced after implementing HMIS and healthcare workers benefit from evidence-based medicine from HMIS	Ujan IA, Bhutto A, Rind MM, Suhaimi MA (2016)

Research Methodology

Data were collected from ward, intensive care unit and emergency department nurses using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire is composed of 2 parts of questions. The first part included demographic details such as gender, age and level of education, years of experience in nursing practice, hours of computer use and formal computer training, and the second part included 15 statements on the hospital's adoption of the improved hospital information system. SPSS version 22 software was used for data analysis. Added a final open-ended question asking nurses for suggestions to increase nurses' acceptance of HIS.

Result

Table 1 presents a descriptive analysis of the demographic details of nurses working in selected hospitals. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among nurses in wards, intensive care units and emergency departments. The valid answer for 389 participants was nurse. Of the respondents, the majority were nurses 311 (80%) and only 78 (20%) were men. Participants ranged in age from 20-29 years 53 (14%) to 50-59 years 39 (10%). Most of them belong to the 30-39 age group (43.7%). Analysis of nurses' education levels showed that 171 (44%) nurses obtained a nursing degree, 209 (54%) obtained a bachelor's degree and nine (2%) obtained a master's degree. Professional experience in nursing practice can range from less than 5 years to more than 25 years. The largest proportion of nurses 140 (36%) had been in practice for 11 to 15 years, followed by 46 (12%) with less than 5 years of experience. Among nurses with previous IT experience, the longest was 3-4 years 189 (49%), followed by 5-9 years 146 (37%). 207 (53%) said they had received formal computer training, while 182 (47%) said they had received no training of any kind.

Table 1 Demographic details of nurses working in tertiary care teaching hospital

Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	78	20%
	Female	311	80%
Age (Years)	20-29	53	14%
	30-39	159	41%
	40-49	138	35%
	50-59	39	10%
	More than 60	0	0
Education Level	Diploma	171	44%
	Bachelor	209	54%
	Master/PhD	09	2%
Year of experience in nursing practice	> 5	46	12%
	6-10	123	32%
	11-15	140	36%
	16-20	58	15%
	21-25	22	6%
	< 25	0	0
Period of computer usage	> 1	16	4%
	1-2	38	10%
	3-4	189	49%
	5-9	146	37%
Formal computer training	Yes	207	53%
	No	182	47%

Table 2 shows a descriptive examination of the frequency and proportion of nurses that accept updating the HIS. The HIS is straightforward to learn and use, according to 239 (61 %) of nurses surveyed. The HIS is straightforward to learn and use, according to 378 (97 %) of the nurses surveyed. The majority of 382 nurses (98 %) indicated the HIS system is a daily aspect of their employment. The information given by the HIS system benefited 62 (16 %) nurses 'work, however there was duplication of effort in the HIS and their area of practice records, while the remaining 327 (84 %) respondents claimed that the details available by the Information system did not facilitate their job. 250 nurses (64 %) agreed that they could get information when and when they needed it. 230 (59 %) of the nurses surveyed indicated they could locate all the information they required, while 159 (41 %) stated they did not need to seek for all the information. Almost 359 (92 %) of nursing responders said the material was frequently updated, while 30

(8 %) did not reply. 382 (98 %) of the 382 nurses stated that the data they recorded was necessary for patient care. Moreover, 385 nurses (99 %) agreed that the data captured in the HIS is reliable, whereas 4 nurses (1 %) did not. 239 nurses (61 %) assessed the HIS as easy to use, accurate, prompt, and user-friendly, while the remaining 150 (39 %) disagreed. A higher number of 357 (92 %) acknowledged to having obtained adequate formal training to use the HIS, although 32 (8 %) respondents agree that IT personnel give acceptable assistance for the HIS, whereas 20 (5 %) do not accept that IT staff do not provide (react promptly) during HIS issues.

Table 2 Nurses acceptability towards the upgraded HIS system

Sl.No.	Nurses acceptability towards the upgraded HIS system	Yes	No
1	It is simple to learn how to utilize the HIS.	239(61%)	150 (39%)
2	It is easy to use HIS	239(61%)	150 (39%)
3	It is easy to know how to accomplish the planned tasks	378 (97%)	11 (3%)
4	The HIS system is part of your daily work	382 (98%)	7 (2%)
5	The information given by the HISsystem makes my job easier	62 (16%)	327 (84%)
6	I can get information when I need it.	250 (64%)	139 (36%)
7	I can access information when I need it	250(64%)	139(36%)
8	I can locate all the data I require.	230 (59%)	159 (41%)
9	Information is always up to date day	359 (92%)	30 (8%)
10	I record information that is crucial for patient care.	382 (98%)	7 (2%)
11	I am confident in the accuracy of the information presented.	385 (99%)	4 (1%)
12	The data that the HIS offers is consistently correct and timely.	239(61%)	150 (39%)
13	The interface of the HIS system has proven to be user-friendly	239(61%)	150(39%)
14	I got sufficient formal training to employ HIS.	357 (92%)	32 (8%)
15	The IT team supported HIS in a sufficient manner.	369 (95%)	20 (5%)

Discussion

In this study, nurses from a few tertiary care teaching hospitals were surveyed to ascertain their opinions on the acceptability of an upgraded hospital information system. According to the findings, nurse traits were substantially and favourably related to adoption of the improved SIS. Important determining criteria for computer usage include gender, age, education level, number of years of nursing experience, length of computer use, and formal computer training. HIS acceptability and user acceptance are positively impacted. These results are in line with those of other research studies in the area that looked at clinician acceptability of the EMR (2, 4, 6, 15). Users self-efficacy, senior management support, and information quality all had significant effects on perceived ease of use, according to Hsiao et al [2011] research. These findings are consistent with the majority of nurses' approval of the improved HIS's integration into everyday practise. The capacity to access the information at any location, discover all the continuously updated information they want, and accept the accuracy of the data gathered, according to nurses, makes their jobs simpler. Similar to this, Lacey (10) said that the adoption of an EMR system might happen quickly if nurses welcome the change. The majority of the nurses in our survey believed that the SIS was simple to learn and use and that they were able to utilise it to carry out the duties it was designed to do. Our findings are in line with earlier discoveries that the system frequently makes their day-to-day tasks easier (1, 3, 5). The findings unmistakably demonstrate how HIS training may successfully assist Saudi hospital nurses in providing high-quality medical care. Zhao, Yu, Li, and Gagnon (2009) found in their study that healthcare planners and managers need to make sure that the adoption of EMR in healthcare institutions is beneficial and simple to use (17). The HIS is simple to understand and utilise, according to our results. Nurses will embrace the SIS more readily if it is made user-friendly and they receive proper training that takes their requirements into consideration. These are important variables that may be

thought of as impacting the HIS's planning and execution (3,6,16). The mastery of HIS-related duties for nurses requires formal training. Nurses will be more receptive to learning and less resistive to change if healthcare companies give the right supporting education (1).

Conclusion & Recommendation

This study acknowledges and acknowledges that nurses are adopting the enhanced SIS because it is easy to learn and easy to use. In order for nurses to accept the upgraded HIS, user demographics were shown to be crucial. Comprehensive training sessions on the use of the HIS should be offered to nurses without formal training on the system to increase adoption. Overall, our findings on nurse demographics and the acceptability of improved HIS point to the significance of further research into nurse acceptance of HIS. Further acceptability research is advised to be done following the introduction of new information systems or if nursing staff exhibits resistance. Lastly, we advise doing more extensive acceptability trials including carers from various healthcare settings. These will encourage improved portrayal and comprehension of nurses' utilisation of hospital information systems.

Reference

1. Ajami S, BertianiZM. Training and its impact on Hospital Information System (HIS) success. *J. Inform. Tech. Softw. Eng*2012;2:112
2. Aldosari B. Factors affecting physicians' attitudes about the medical information system usage and acceptance through the mandated implementation of integrated medical Information system at the Saudi Arabia National Guard Health System: a modified technology acceptance model. *DissAbstrInt*2003;64:3169B.
3. Ismail, A. Jamil, A. Fareed, A T. Rahman A, Madihah, J , Bakar A &Saadi H, The implementation of Hospital Information System (HIS) in tertiary hospitals in malaysia: a qualitative study, (2012).
4. Alquraini H, Alhashem AM, Shah MA, Chowdhury RI. Factors influencing nurses' attitudes towards the use of computerized health information systems in Kuwaiti hospitals. *J AdvNurs*2007;57:375–81
5. BakheetAldosari, Sheema Al-Mansour, HananAldosari, et al (2017), Assessment of factors influencing nurses acceptance of electronic medical record in a Saudi Arabia hospital, *Journal Informatics in Medicine Unlocked* 10 (2018) 82–88
6. Huryk LA. Factors influencing nurses' attitudes towards healthcare information technology. *J NursManag* 2010; 18:606–12.
7. Hsiao JL, Chang HC, Chen RF. A study of factors affecting acceptance of hospital information systems: a nursing perspective. *J Nurs Res* 2011; 19:150–60
8. Hwang JI, Park HA. Nurses' attitude toward computerization and their need assessment in pre and post hospital information systems. *J. Korean. Soc. Med.Inform* 2001;7:57–66.
9. Imran A. U. (2016) “Assessing the Acceptance of HMIS by Healthcare professionals of Pakistan, MS thesis, IIUM,
10. Khalifa M, Alswailem O. Hospital information systems (HIS) acceptance and satisfaction: a case study of a tertiary care hospital. *Procedia Computer Science*. 2015 Jan 1; 63:198-204
11. Lacey DG. Nurses' attitudes towards computerization: a review of the literature. *J NursManag*1993; 1:239–43.
12. Buntin MB, Burke MF, Hoaglin MC. & Blumenthal D, the benefits of health information technology: a review of the recent literature shows predominantly positive results. *Health affairs*, 30(3) 2011, 464-471.
13. OtienoOG, Toyama H, Asonuma M, Kanai-Pak M, Naitoh K. Nurses' views on the use, quality and user satisfaction with electronic medical records: questionnaire development. *J AdvNurs* 2007:209–19.

14. Ketikidis P, Dimitrovski T, L. Lazuras&. Bath PA, Acceptance of Health Information technology in health professionals: an application of the revised technology acceptance model. *Health Informatics Journal*, 18(2) 2012, 124-134.
15. Qazi MS, Ali M: Pakistan's Health Management Information System: health managers' perspectives. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2009, 59:10-14.
16. Ujan IA, Bhutto A, Rind MM, Suhaimi MA: Acceptance of HMIS by healthcare professionals of private sector hospitals of Pakistan. *SURJ (Science Series)*. 2016, 48:
17. Yu P, Li H, Gagnon M. Health IT acceptance factors in long-term care facilities: a cross-sectional survey. *Int. J. Med. Inform* 2009:219–29.